

Synthesis, spectral characterization and ligation behaviour of phenylmercury(II) *O,O'*-dialkyl/alkylene dithiophosphates

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Abstract : The phenylmercury(II) complexes having composition $[C_6H_5Hg\{S(S)P(OCH_2CH_2OCH_3)_2\}]$, $[C_6H_5Hg\{S(S)POCH_2C(CH_3)_2CH_2O\}]$ and $[C_6H_5HgS(S)POCH_2C(CH_3)_2CH\{CH(CH_3)_2\}O]$ were prepared by the reaction of phenylmercury(II) acetate with NH_4 salt of *O,O'*-dialkyl/alkylene dithiophosphate in absolute methanol at room temperature. The complexes were characterized by their analytical data, IR, 1H and ^{31}P NMR spectra. Ligation behaviour of the complexes has been established by reacting them with CdI_2 , $AgOCOCF_3$, $AgOCCl_3$, $AgSCN$, $HgCl_2$, $Hg(OCOCCl_3)_2$, $Hg(OCOCF_3)_2$ and $Hg(SCN)_2$. The bimetallic adducts were formed through the coordination of the sulfur atom of phenylmercury(II) *O,O'*-dialkyl/alkylene dithiophosphate to the soft metal acceptors.

Keywords : Bimetallic complex, phenyl mercury, dialkyl/alkylene dithiophosphate.

The tendency of dithiophosphate is to act as a bridge between two metals via the sulfur atoms to form bimetallic complexes are scarce and a few such compounds have been reported¹. Earlier we have reported the reactivity of phenylmercury alkylene² and organotin *O,O'*-dialkyl/alkylene dithiophosphate³ towards Lewis acids. Corresponding work on phenylmercury with dithiophosphate derivatives of 2-methoxy ethanol, 2,2,4-trimethyl 1,3-pentane diol and 2,2-dimethyl 1,3-propane diol are not known.

In the present communication we report the preparation, spectral characterization and ligation behaviour of some phenylmercury(II) *O,O'*-dialkyl/alkylene dithiophosphate with Ag^I , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} .

Results and discussion

Phenylmercury acetate reacts with ammonium *O,O'*-dialkyl/alkylene dithiophosphates in 1 : 1 molar ratio in absolute methanol, to afford white complexes as shown below :

The 1 : 1 bimetallic adducts of phenylmercury(II) *O,O'*-dialkyl/alkylene dithiophosphate with metal acceptors, such as Ag^I , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} were obtained by stirring a mixture of the two components in absolute methanol at room temperature.

The analytical data of newly synthesized phenylmercury(II) *O,O'*-dialkyl/alkylene dithiophosphates are as : [A] yield 75%, cream, m.p. 85°, Hg 38.24 (38.38); S 12.39 (12.24%); [B], yield 90%, m.p. 102°, Hg 43.22 (43.33);

Table 1. Analytical data of $[C_6H_5HgS(S)P(OCH_2CH_2OCH_3)_2].LA$

Sl no.	LA	Colour	Decomp. temp. (°C)	Yield (%)	Elemental analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)			
					Hg	Cd	Ag	S
1.	HgCl ₂	White	230	70	50.39 (50.52)	-	-	7.93 (8.07)
2.	CdI ₂	Green	240	65	22.42 (22.56)	12.52 (12.64)	-	7.12 (7.21)
3.	Hg(OCOCF ₃) ₂	White	170	78	42.38 (42.20)	-	-	7.62 (6.75)
4.	Hg(OCOCCl ₃) ₂	Grey	83	70	38.10 (38.28)	-	-	6.21 (6.11)
5.	Hg(SCN) ₂	Grey	76	67	47.90 (47.79)	-	-	15.12 (15.05)
6.	AgOCOCF ₃	Green	230	85	26.86 (26.98)	-	14.42 (14.50)	8.36 (8.48)
7.	AgOCOCCl ₃	Yellow	156	90	25.36 (25.29)	-	12.64 (13.60)	7.96 (8.08)
8.	AgSCN	Yellow	120	70	29.22 (29.13)	-	15.74 (15.66)	13.87 (13.96)

S 13.73 (13.85%); [C], yield 90%, m.p. 116°, Hg 38.69 (38.82); S 13.26 (13.38%) which indicate 1 : 1 [C_6H_5Hg : dtp] stoichiometry. The products are solid, stable at room temperature, and are not affected by the atmospheric oxygen and moisture. They are partially soluble in $CHCl_3$ but soluble in DMSO.

The analytical data for the bimetallic adducts for [A] is given in Table 1[†]. They are of 1 : 1 (donor : acceptor) stoichiometry, solid and stable at room temperature. The adducts are insoluble in common organic solvents but soluble in DMSO.

The molar conductance data ($2.97-3.46 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$) of phenylmercury(II) *O, O'*-dialkyl/alkylene dithiophosphates and their bimetallic complexes have been found to be much lower than the value expected for any electrolyte and hence these may be considered to behave as non-electrolytic in DMSO.

IR spectra :

The FTIR of phenylmercury(II) *O, O'*-dialkyl/alkylene dithiophosphates were recorded in the range $4000-450 \text{cm}^{-1}$ in KBr/CsI. The bands present at $1015, 919$ and 659cm^{-1} (dialkyl dithiophosphate) and at $1040 \pm 2, 804 \pm 1$ and 683 ± 14 (alkylene dithiophosphate) are assigned to $[v(P)-O-C]$, $[vP-O-(C)]$ and $v(P=S)$ respec-

tively^{2,4}.

The band of medium intensity at 530cm^{-1} (dialkyl dithiophosphate) and $512 \pm 2 \text{cm}^{-1}$ (alkylene dithiophosphate) may be attributed to the $v(P-S)$ vibration respectively, and invariably indicates the presence of the unidentate *O, O'*-dialkyl/alkylene dithiophosphate group attached to phenylmercury moiety^{2,4}. A weak band at $455 \pm 2 \text{cm}^{-1}$ may be assigned to the stretching mode of vibration of the phenyl ring attached to mercury atom².

In the IR spectra of the bimetallic adducts of phenylmercury(II) *O, O'*-dialkyl/alkylene dithiophosphate. LA (LA referred to eq. (2)), absorption due to $v(P=S)$ is shifted to lower frequency and appears at $650 \pm 2 \text{cm}^{-1}$ (dialkyl dithiophosphate) and $675 \pm 16 \text{cm}^{-1}$ (alkylene dithiophosphate). Absorption due to $v(P-S)$ remains almost unaffected indicating the presence of the unidentate *O, O'*-dialkyl/alkylene dithiophosphate group.

The two absorptions associated with $[v(P)-O-C]$ and $[vP-O-(C)]$ appear at $1020 \pm 2 \text{cm}^{-1}, 925 \pm 2 \text{cm}^{-1}$ (dialkyl dithiophosphate) and at $1044 \pm 2 \text{cm}^{-1}, 812 \pm 2 \text{cm}^{-1}$ (alkylene dithiophosphate) respectively in the bimetallic adducts. The considerable lowering of the $v(P=S)$ frequency indicates coordination of the sulfur atoms of the ligand to the mercury and soft metal acceptors. There is a shift of electron density from oxygen and carbon

[†]Persons interested in analytical data of [B] and [C] may contact authors.

Table 2. ^1H and ^{31}P NMR spectral data of representative compounds

Sl. no. Compd.	Aryl protons (δ , ppm)	Alkyl/Alkylene protons (δ , ppm)	^{31}P
1. $[\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{HgS}(\text{S})\text{P}(\text{OCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OCH}_3)_2]$	7.21–7.40 (5H, m, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{-Hg}$)	4.11–4.17 (4H, dt, OCH_2), 3.55–3.58 (4H, t, CH_2), 3.25 (6H, s, OCH_3)	-
2. $[\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{HgS}(\text{S})\text{POCH}_2\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CH}_2\text{O}]$	7.20–7.43 (5H, m, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{-Hg}$)	3.94–4.04 (4H, d, OCH_2), 0.97 (6H, s, CH_3)	-
3. $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{Hg}[\text{S}(\text{S})\text{POCH}_2\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CH}\{\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2\}\text{O}]$	-	-	72.53
4. $[\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{HgS}(\text{S})\text{P}(\text{OCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OCH}_3)_2] \text{AgOCOCCl}_3$	7.19–7.04 (5H, m, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{-Hg}$)	4.12–4.18 (4H, m, OCH_2), 3.56–3.59 (4H, t, CH_2), 3.27 (6H, s, OCH_3)	-
5. $[\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{HgS}(\text{S})\text{POCH}_2\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CH}_2\text{O}] \text{HgCl}_2$	7.26–7.38 (5H, m, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{-Hg}$)	4.08–4.13 (4H, d, OCH_2), 1.10 (6H, s, CH_3)	-
6. $[\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{HgS}(\text{S})\text{POCH}_2\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CHO}] \cdot \text{Hg}(\text{OCOCF}_3)_2$	7.26–7.39 (5H, m, $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{-Hg}$)	4.07–4.12 (4H, d, OCH_2), 1.11 (6H, s, OCH_3)	-
7. $[\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{HgS}(\text{S})\text{POCH}_2\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CH}\{\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2\}\text{P}]\cdot\text{CdI}_2$	-	-	80.9

through phosphorus and sulfur to the soft metal atom, which increases the bond order of the C–O and P–O bonds. The $\nu(\text{Hg-Ph})$ stretching mode of vibration remains almost unaffected and appears at $455 \pm 2 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The $\nu(\text{Hg-S})$ stretching mode of vibration would not be identified as they lie beyond the recorded range of spectra.

The thiocyanate group is S-bonded since $\nu(\text{SCN})$, $\nu(\text{C=S})$ and $\delta(\text{SCN})$ appears at $\sim 2092 \pm 8$, 730 ± 2 and 468 cm^{-1} respectively⁵. The trifluoroacetate group is unidentate⁶ since $\nu_{\text{asy}}(\text{OCO})$ and $\nu_{\text{sym}}(\text{OCO})$ appear at 1685 ± 5 and $1430 \pm 5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively, with $-\Delta\nu = 250 \pm 5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The trichloroacetate group is unidentately coordinated^{6,7} as $\nu_{\text{asy}}(\text{OCO})$ and $\nu_{\text{sym}}(\text{OCO})$ are located at $1680 \pm 5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $1340 \pm 5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively, with $-\Delta\nu = 340 \pm 10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. Absorption due to Hg–Cl and Cd–I stretching modes could not be identified as they lie beyond the recorded range of the spectra.

^1H and ^{31}P NMR spectra :

In the ^1H NMR spectra (Table 2) of $[\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{HgS}(\text{S})\text{P}(\text{OCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OCH}_3)_2]$, the $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{Hg}$ signals appear at 7.21–7.40 ppm. A double triplet appearing at 4.11–4.17 ppm is assigned to OCH_2 . One triplet appear at 3.55–3.58 ppm for CH_2 and a singlet at 3.25 ppm is due to OCH_3 , whereas in the ^1H NMR spectra of $[\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{HgS}(\text{S})\text{POCH}_2\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CH}_2\text{O}]$, the $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{Hg}$ signals appear at 7.20–7.43 ppm. A doublet and a singlet appearing 3.94–4.04 and 0.97 ppm are assigned to OCH_2 and CH_3 respectively.

In the ^1H NMR spectra of $[\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{HgS}(\text{S})\text{P}(\text{OCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OCH}_3)_2] \cdot \text{AgOCOCCl}_3$, $[\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{HgS}(\text{S})\text{POCH}_2\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CH}_2\text{O}] \cdot \text{Hg}(\text{OCOCF}_3)_2$ and $[\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{HgS}(\text{S})\text{POCH}_2\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CH}_2\text{O}] \cdot \text{HgCl}_2$ the de-shielding of alkyl/alkylene protons viz. OCH_2 , CH_2 , OCH_3 and CH_3 in bimetallic adducts indicates considerable shift of electron density from dithiophosphates moiety to the soft metal atom through sulfur. In the bimetallic adducts higher de-shielding of alkyl/alkylene protons favour the presence of bridging ligands^{8,9} which support the result obtained from the infrared spectral data.

In the $^{31}\text{P}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR spectra (Table 2) of $[\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{HgS}(\text{S})\text{POCH}_2\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CH}\{\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2\}\text{O}]$, a single peak is observed at $\delta 72.53$ ppm and the low chemical shift value compared to parent ligand (66.52 ppm) further confirm the unidentate mode of bonding of the dithiophosphate moiety¹⁰.

However, the $^{31}\text{P}\{^1\text{H}\}$ NMR spectra of $[\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{HgS}(\text{S})\text{POCH}_2\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CH}\{\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2\}\text{O}] \cdot \text{CdI}_2$ show deshielding of the phosphorus atom to an extent of about $\delta 7.4$ ppm from the parent phenylmercury(II) 2,2,4-trimethyl-1,3-pentane dithiophosphate and a peak at $\delta 80.92$ ppm is observed. The deshielding of the phosphorus atom in bimetallic adducts supports the results obtained from IR and ^1H NMR spectra.

On the basis of analytical and spectral (IR, ^1H and ^{31}P NMR) evidences and support from the previous work^{1,2}, a linear structure containing a unidentate dithiophosphate

group and a two coordinated mercury atom² is assigned to phenylmercury(II) *O, O'*-dialkyl/alkylene dithiophosphate. The tentative structures are given below.

R = $-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OCH}_3$; G = $-\text{CH}_2\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CH}_2-$,
 $-\text{CH}_2\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CHCH}(\text{CH}_3)_2-$

In case of bimetallic adducts it may be concluded that the two molecules of metal acceptors are bound to two different sulfur atoms. The dithiophosphate group thus acts as a bridge between phenylmercury and soft metal. The following structures may be proposed for phenylmercury(II) *O, O'*-dialkyl/alkylene dithiophosphate. LA.

LA = AgOCOCF_3 , AgOCOCCl_3 , AgSCN , $\text{Hg}(\text{OCOCCl}_3)_2$,
 $\text{Hg}(\text{OCOCF}_3)_2$, $\text{Hg}(\text{SCN})_2$, HgCl_2 , CdI_2

In these bimetallic adducts, Hg^{II} and Cd^{II} are tricoordinated¹¹⁻¹³ while Ag^{I} possess a coordination number two¹⁴.

Experimental

Phenylmercury acetate (Aldrich) was used as such. Solvents were dried and purified by standard procedures¹⁵ *O, O'*-dialkyl/alkylene dithiophosphoric acids and their ammonium salts were prepared according to an established procedure¹⁶. The molar conductance of the compounds were measured using a dip-type conductivity cell on a Decible conductivity meter model DC 610 in anhydrous DMSO. Metal contents and sulfur were determined by a reported procedure¹⁷. FTIR spectra were recorded on a Bruker IFS66V (KBr/CsI, 4000–450 cm^{-1}) ¹H and ³¹P NMR spectra were recorded at 300 MHz and 121.5 MHz on a Bruker DRX 300FT NMR spectrophotometer using TMS (as an internal standard) and H_3PO_4 (as an external standard) respectively in CDCl_3 and DMSO (d_6).

Reaction of $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{HgOCOCH}_3$ and $\text{NH}_4[\text{S}(\text{S})\text{P}(\text{OCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OCH}_3)_2]$: Phenylmercury acetate (3.36 g, 10

mmol) and ammonium salt *O, O'*-di-2-methoxy ethyl dithiophosphoric acid (2.36 g, 10 mmol) in absolute methanol was stirred at room temperature for six hours. The precipitated product was filtered, washed several times with methanol, finally with diethyl ether to produce analytically pure product and dried *in vacuo*. The reactions of $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{HgOCOCH}_3$ with $[\text{NH}_4\text{S}(\text{S})\text{POCH}_2\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CH}\{\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2\}\text{O}]$ and $[\text{NH}_4\text{S}(\text{S})\text{POCH}_2\text{C}(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CH}_2\text{O}]$ were carried out similarly.

Reaction of phenyl mercury(II) O, O'-dialkyl/alkylene dithiophosphates and soft metal acceptors: In a representative experiment, to a solution of phenylmercury(II) *O, O'*-di-2-methoxy ethyl dithiophosphate (0.552 g, 1 mmol) in absolute methanol and HgCl_2 (0.272 g, 1 mmol) in the same solvent were stirred together at room temperature for about 4 h. The precipitated product was filtered and washed several times with methanol, finally with diethyl ether to produce analytically pure product and dried *in vacuo*.

Similar bimetallic products were prepared using $\text{Hg}(\text{SCN})_2$, $\text{Hg}(\text{OCOCCl}_3)_2$, $\text{Hg}(\text{OCOCF}_3)_2$, CdI_2 , AgSCN , AgOCOCCl_3 , AgOCOCF_3 as acceptors with all phenylmercury(II) *O, O'*-dialkyl/alkylene dithiophosphate.

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